

ELECTRICAL ENGINEERING

METHODS OF FORECASTING THE PRODUCTION OF SOLAR MODULES AND BATTERIES BASED ON METEOROLOGICAL DATA

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Abstract

The development of electronic systems based on renewable energy sources (RES) has made it possible to distinguish this class of energy sources into a separate energy sector. According to the forecasts of the European Photovoltaic Industry Association (EPIA), solar energy will displace oil and nuclear energy in the future. In the world, the annual growth of solar energy over the past five years has averaged about 50%. The energy obtained on the basis of solar radiation will hypothetically be able to provide 20-25% of humanity's electricity needs by 2050 and reduce carbon dioxide emissions.

Solar cells are considered the main choice for long-term power generation for satellites and space systems. This is mainly due to their high power-to-weight ratio and good scalability of solar modules in accordance with the power requirements of the space mission. The constant and significant increase in the efficiency of the devices has enabled the operation of advanced space systems, such as the International Space Station, rovers and satellites [1].

Keywords: renewable energy, solar cells, short and medium-term forecasting, machine learning.

Data analysis

The Python programming language was used to analyze meteorological data, and the pandas, seaborn, matplotlib and numpy libraries were used as packages. Datasets located on the "Open Power System Data" platform were used as data. The search for correlations in the data based on pairwise relations for meteorological weather indicators, as well as finding correlations using the Pearson correlation coefficient, was carried out.

Table 1 shows the correlation coefficients for each weather metric using the Pearson correlation coefficient. The main information parameters used for data analysis are: $v1$ – wind speed; $SWTDN$ – the value of the intensity of solar radiation to the atmosphere, W/m^2 ; $SWGDN$ – the value of the intensity of solar radiation on a horizontal platform near the ground, W/m^2 ; T – temperature, K ; ρ – the density of air at the surface, kg/m^3 ; p – air pressure, Pa .

Table 1

Correlation matrix

	<i>Solar Intensity</i>	<i>SWGDN</i>	<i>SWTDN</i>	<i>T</i>	<i>rho</i>	<i>p</i>	<i>v1</i>
<i>Solar Intensity</i>	1	0,95	0,86	0,79	-0,73	0,06	-0,39
<i>SWGDN</i>	0,95	1	0,93	0,79	-0,74	0,04	-0,38
<i>SWTDN</i>	0,86	0,93	1	0,79	-0,78	-0,1	-0,33
<i>T</i>	0,79	0,79	0,79	1	-0,95	0,017	-0,31
<i>rho</i>	-0,73	-0,74	-0,78	-0,95	1	0,28	0,22
<i>p</i>	0,06	0,04	-0,1	0,017	0,28	1	-0,25
<i>v1</i>	-0,39	-0,38	-0,33	-0,31	0,22	-0,25	1

The Python programming language was used to predict the generation of solar models. Pandas and numpy libraries were used as packages for working with data, seaborn and matplotlib were used for visualization, and sklearn was used as a library for machine learning.

The analyzed dataset should be divided into training and test samples. The separation will be carried out by sequentially cutting 80% of the sample to the training set (January-October 2017), and the remaining 20%

to the training set (October–December 2017). As the correct answers (y) for the model, the data of the `DE_solar_generation_actual` column will be used, and the signs (X) for training will be: $SWGDN$, $SWTDN$, T , ρ , p , $v1$, $v2$, v_{50m} , $z0$.

There are various training parameters in the models, automatic selection of model parameters – GridSearch (lattice search algorithm) will be used to minimize the error.

Forecasting output

Least Squares Regression Line is a simple and widely used method for estimating the relationship between a dependent variable or response variable, such as solar radiation intensity, and a set of independent variables or predictors. Regression minimizes the sum of the squares of the differences between the observed

intensity of the Sun and the intensity of the Sun predicted by a linear approximation of forecast weather indicators.

Thus, the target function is *SolarIntensity*, and *Pressure*, *Temperature*, *WindSpeed*, *SkyCover*, *SWGDN*, *SWTDN*, *Z* are the parameters of the function $F(1)$:

$$\text{SolarIntensity} = F(\text{SWGDN}, \text{SWTDN}, \text{Temperature}, \text{SkyCover}, \text{Pressure}, \text{WindSpeed1}, \text{WindSpeed2}, \text{WindSpeed}_{50m}, z_0). \quad (1)$$

First of all we need to apply *Least Squares Regression Line* method to eight-month training data [2]. After training, the *LinearRegression* model with coefficients for each weather metric is presented in the formula (5.2):

$$\begin{aligned} \text{SolarIntensity} = & 688 + 17,70 \cdot \text{SWGDN} + 4,12 \cdot \text{SWTDN} - \\ & -264,57 \cdot T - 590,58 \cdot \text{rho} + 78,44 \cdot p - 11,02 \cdot v_1 + \\ & + 123,81 \cdot v_2 - 30,432 \cdot v_{50m} + 105,81 \cdot z_0. \end{aligned} \quad (2)$$

Using the obtained multiple regression equation (2), we can construct a forecast graph of the predicted target variable and real (test) data (Figure 1).

Figure 1 – Results of forecasting the generation of FES (a) and the influence of atmospheric parameters (b, c) Linear Regression

We can apply the penalizing linear *Ridge* model on the training data. After training, the *Ridge* model with coefficients for each weather metric is presented in formula (3):

$$\begin{aligned} \text{SolarIntensity} = & -700,18 + 17,88 \cdot \text{SWGDN} + 3,43 \cdot \text{SWTDN} - \\ & -593,46 \cdot T - 200,83 \cdot \text{rho} + 5,52 \cdot p - 96,67 \cdot v_1 + \\ & + 39,06 \cdot v_2 - 7,405 \cdot v_{50m} + 46,18 \cdot z_0 \end{aligned} \quad (3)$$

Using the obtained multiple regression equation (3), we will plot the forecast of the predicted target variable and real (test) data (Figure 2).

(b) (c)
Figure 2 – Results of forecasting the generation of FES
(a) and the influence of atmospheric parameters (b, c) Ridge

We can apply the Lasso penalizing linear model on the training data. After training, the Lasso model with coefficients for each weather metric is presented in formula (4):

$$\begin{aligned} SolarIntensity = & 269,91 + 17,51 \cdot SWGDN + 3,90 \cdot SWTDN - \\ & -11,5 \cdot T - 261,35 \cdot rho + 37,79 \cdot p - 68,93 \cdot v1 + \\ & +55,86 \cdot v2 - 51,24 \cdot v_{50m} + 74,89 \cdot z0 \end{aligned} \quad (4)$$

Using the obtained multiple regression equation (4), we will plot the forecast of the predicted target variable and real (test) data (Figure 3).

(a)

(b)

(c)

Figure 3 – Results of forecasting the generation of FES (a) and the influence of atmospheric parameters (b, c) Lasso

Note that linear regression without penalty and Lasso regression behave similarly, and this is observed in Figures 5.1 (c) and 5.3 (c). It is obvious that the importance of the features is approximately the same, and the difference from Ridge regression.

Figure 4 shows the results of forecasting output using the *DecisionTreeRegressor*.

(a)

Figure 4 – Results of forecasting the generation of FES (a) and the influence of atmospheric parameters (b, c) DecisionTreeRegressor

Figure 5 shows the results of forecasting output using RandomForestRegressor.

Figure 5 – Results of forecasting the generation of FES (a) and the influence of atmospheric parameters (b, c) RandomForestRegressor

Figure 6 shows the results of forecasting output using Gradient Boosting Regressor.

Figure 6 – Results of forecasting the generation of FES (a) and the influence of atmospheric parameters (b, c) GradientBoostingRegressor

As can be seen from all the graphs, the determining factor is the level of insolation at the surface, however, this parameter is variable and in itself depends on the level of clouds and humidity.

Model quality assessment

We can evaluate the quality of the obtained models using the criteria: mean quadratic error (MSE), R² statistics and average absolute error.

Table 2 shows quality metrics for linear models, and table 3 shows quality metrics for wood models.

Table 2

Quality metrics for linear models				
Nº in order	Forecasting method	Mean squared error (MSE)	Mean absolute error (MAE)	R ²
1	LinearRegression	387,92	16710,52	0,765 (mean) ± 0,1084 (std)
2	Ridge	209,98	11883,01	0,757 (mean) ± 0,1343 (std)
3	Lasso	301,35	14677,08	0,772 (mean) ± 0,0831 (std)

Table 3

Quality metrics for wood models

№ in order	Forecasting method	Mean squared error	Mean absolute error	R ²
1	<i>DecisionTreeRegressor</i>	79,53	4001,56	0,869 (mean) ± 0,0657 (std)
2	<i>RandomForestRegressor</i>	34,43	4204,331	0,935 (mean) ± 0,0287 (std)
3	<i>GradientBoostingRegressor</i>	23,71	2533,645	0,937 (mean) ± 0,0279 (std)

It is seen from Table 2 that among simple linear models, the Ridge regression model showed the best result for all the quality metrics under consideration.

It is seen from Table 3, that among the wooden models, the best result for all the considered quality metrics was shown by a model based on boosting – *GradientBoostingRegressor*. The model with the use of bagging – *RandomForestRegressor* coped a little worse.

Conclusion

The most promising model was the *Gradient Boosting Regressor*, which provides the minimum absolute and quadratic errors, as well as the maximum

mean metric R² and the minimum spread (std) on 10 data segments.

References

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